

Administrative Requirements as One of the Pillars for Implementing E-Management in Sports Institutions

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the extent to which administrative requirements are met in sports institutions and their contribution to implementing electronic management. To achieve this, the descriptive method was applied to a randomly selected sample of 64 administrators. A questionnaire was utilized as a tool for data and information collection. The findings revealed that administrative requirements contribute to the implementation of e-management in sports institutions. Therefore, the study recommends focusing on training administrative staff in sports institutions in information and communication technologies to meet the demands of e-management efficiently, to the explosive strength requirement of the discipline.

Introduction

The world has recently witnessed numerous changes and transformations across various domains and sectors, significantly affecting the operational environments of many organizations and institutions. In light of these developments, especially the digital revolution in information and communication technologies, it has become essential for institutions to capitalize on these advancements and the qualitative leap they offer in all fields by adopting e-management as a modern administrative approach. Based on this premise, e-management represents the optimal investment in contemporary information technologies and systems, enabling efficient administrative performance across all practices and organizational levels, while minimizing effort, cost, and time. In this regard, (Hafid, 2021, p. 283) describes e-management as the harnessing and usage of various technical resources to deliver a wide range of services.

With the rise of digital transformation and the adoption of e-management initiatives, especially within sports organizations and institutions, this transition has become a necessary step toward improving performance, enhancing management efficiency, and reducing administrative burdens. However, for e-management to be effectively implemented and sustained, it necessitates a supportive working environment underpinned by various essential elements and prerequisites, chief among them being administrative requirements. Researcher Amel Mohamed determines these administrative requirements as among the most critical components contributing to the success of e-management projects (Amel Mohamed, 2022, p. 147). Dahmani and Djoudi (2017) demonstrated that the necessary administrative requirements enable sports institutions to perform multiple administrative functions with high efficiency. Azzouz and Houiche (2021) highlighted the importance of giving significant attention to management concepts and applying various continuous improvement mechanisms as a modern administrative approach to promote managerial efficiency and develop modern administrative

methods, considering them as one of the key components for implementing e-management in sports institutions.

The presence of such requirements in sports institutions enables their restructuring in innovative ways that align with the evolving digital landscape. It also supports the development of e-administrative leadership capable of effectively managing technological elements and circumstances, promoting innovation, streamlining administrative processes, shaping organizational culture, designing strategic plans and policies, and clearly defining objectives across all administrative levels. Furthermore, the adoption of well-formulated strategies by top management to activate and strengthen e-management becomes an essential prerequisite. Therefore, this study aims to identify the current state of e-management in sports institutions and assess the extent to which administrative requirements contribute to its implementation, given the significant impact that e-management now exerts on these institutions.

Notably, numerous studies have addressed the variables examined in this research and have emphasized the contribution of administrative requirements to the implementation of e-management in organizations. One such study was conducted by Rabie Shafiq Lotfi Atir (2017), which aimed to evaluate the availability of several requirements for implementing e-management in private schools. The study employed a descriptive survey method and utilized a questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. A randomly selected sample of 100 private school principals participated in the study. The results revealed that material, technical, and human requirements received high ratings, whereas administrative and security requirements were rated as moderate.

Another study was conducted by Samira Matar Al-Massaoudi in Saudi Arabia (2010), which explored the different obstacles to implementing e-management and identified the most prominent mechanisms suggested to overcome these obstacles from the perspective of human resources managers and employees. The study employed a descriptive method and selected a sample of 100 individuals from HR managers and staff. A questionnaire was utilized as the research instrument. One of the key results was the presence of administrative, human, technical,

and financial obstacles to implementing e-management in the institution under study.

In light of the above, the following problem statement is raised: To what extent are administrative requirements available in sports institutions, and how much do they contribute to the activation of e-management components within them?

This problematic branches into the following sub-questions:

- To what extent are administrative requirements available in sports institutions?
- What is the level of e-management implementation in the sports institution under study?
- Do administrative requirements contribute to the implementation of e-management in sports institutions?

2. Methodology and Tools

2.1. Sample and Sampling Method:

The study population consisted of administrators working in the Directorates of Youth and Sports in the provinces of M'Sila and Djelfa. Due to the relatively small size of the study population, a comprehensive survey method was employed to select a representative sample. The total number of participants was 64 administrators from the aforementioned directorates.

2.2. Study Procedures:

2.2.1. Methodology:

The analytical descriptive method was adopted, as it is suitable for the subject of the study.

2.2.2. Variables and Measurement:

- **Independent variable:** Administrative requirements
- **Dependent variable:** Components of e-management

2.2.3. Instrument:

The researcher considered the most accurate and appropriate tool for collecting data and information in this study to be the questionnaire. It consisted of 16 items covering the subject of the study, divided into two axes:

- **Administrative Requirements Axis:** 8 items
- **E-Management in Sports Institutions Axis:** 8 items

A five-point Likert scale was used (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree).

Scientific Foundations of the Instrument:
First: Reliability and Validity of the Administrative Requirements Axis

Table 01: Reliability and validity of the administrative requirements axis.

Validity and Reliability Axis	Validity Coefficient	Reliability Coefficient
Administrative Requirements Axis	0.93	0.94

Source: Prepared by the researcher

In this table, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the Administrative Requirements axis is 0.94, demonstrating a high level of reliability. This positive value reflects strong consistency and coherence among the questionnaire items. The Pearson correlation coefficient reached 0.93, which is statistically significant, concluding that the questionnaire is valid due to the internal consistency of its items.

Second: Reliability and Validity of the E-Management Axis

Table 02: Reliability and validity of the E-Management axis.

Validity and Reliability Axis	Validity Coefficient	Reliability Coefficient
Administrative Requirements Axis	0.93	0.95

Source: Prepared by the researcher

From the table above, it is clear that the questionnaire indicates a high level of reliability, as demonstrated by the positive Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.95. The same table also reveals that the Pearson correlation coefficient is statistically significant, with a value of 0.93. Thus, this questionnaire is valid, as its items are consistent with one another and with the overall questionnaire.

2.3. Statistical Tools

The following statistical tools were employed in this study: Pearson correlation coefficient, Cronbach's Alpha for measuring reliability,

mean, standard deviation, and simple linear regression. To identify differences, the F-test for statistical significance was utilized. To compare two independent samples, the T-test for statistical significance was applied, along with Levene's test (F) for testing homogeneity of variance.

3. Results

Description of the Results for the First Axis:

Table 03: Means and standard deviations for the Administrative Requirements axis.

Item	Simple size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Item 01	64	3.33	1.007
Item 02	64	3.21	1.136
Item 03	64	3.21	1.086
Item 04	64	3.36	1.906
Item 05	64	3.29	1.070
Item 06	64	3.34	1.019
Item 07	64	3.18	1.136
Item 08	64	3.34	1.007
Overall	64	3.27	1.170

Source: Prepared by the researcher

From the table indicating the multiple responses of the study sample to each item of the axis, along with the values of the means and standard deviations, it is noticed that all items fall within the moderate range (2.60–3.40). Item number (06) recorded the highest mean score of 3.36 with a standard deviation of 1.019, demonstrating a moderate level of response from the participants. This serves as a positive indicator of the availability of various administrative requirements in sports institutions and their significance in supporting the implementation of e-management.

The table also demonstrates that the overall mean was 3.27, which also falls within the moderate range. This suggests that the participants' attitudes are generally positive, enabling us to conclude that, according to the responses of the study sample, administrative requirements are moderately available in sports institutions.

Description of the Results for the Second Axis:

Table 03: Means and standard deviations for the E-Management Implementation axis.

Item	Simple size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Item 01	64	3.23	1.111
Item 02	64	3.26	1.136
Item 03	64	3.15	1.096
Item 04	64	3.10	1.930
Item 05	64	3.20	1.070
Item 06	64	3.30	1.119
Item 07	64	3.38	1.136
Item 08	64	3.34	1.027
Overall	64	3.24	1.203

Source: Prepared by the researcher

From the table indicating the various responses of the study sample to each item of the axis, along with the extracted values of the arithmetic means and standard deviations, it is observed that all items fall within the moderate range (2.60–3.40). Item number (07) recorded the highest mean score of 3.38, with a standard deviation of 1.136, demonstrating a moderate level of response from the participants. This is a positive indicator for the items associated with the implementation of e-management in sports institutions.

The table also indicates that the overall mean, which reached 3.24, falls within the moderate range. This suggests that the participants' attitudes are generally positive, concluding that the level of e-management implementation in sports institutions is moderate, based on the responses of the study sample.

Description of the Results of the Third Hypothesis:

Table 04: Interaction relationship between the study variables.

Study Variables		Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Significance Level	Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	R ²	Interpretation
	Administrative Requirements	0.798	0.00	0.649	0.247	The effect size is large.
	E-Management					
	Sample Size	64				
The correlation is statistically significant at the alpha level ($\alpha = 0.01$).						

From the table presenting the various obtained values, it is apparent that there is a positive correlation between the study's two variables, as demonstrated by the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.79, which is positive. Additionally, the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.64, showing a significant effect, as it exceeds the threshold of 0.20. Moreover, the coefficient of determination itself was high, exceeding 0.14, with a value of 0.24, confirming that the variance in the dependent variable is influenced by the variance in the independent variable. This degree of overlap reflects a strong effect size.

Furthermore, the finding was statistically significant at the alpha level ($\alpha = 0.01$). Thus, all these values and results confirm the hypothesis that:

Administrative requirements contribute to the activation of e-management components in sports institutions.

4. Discussion

The findings obtained indicate that the availability of administrative requirements in sports institutions for the implementation of e-management is moderate. This suggests that administrative requirements are among the most crucial foundations and enablers of e-management, as they are essential for developing strategies and frameworks necessary for implementation. These requirements allow top management to plan, organize, monitor, direct, and coordinate

efforts across departments to establish a comprehensive e-management strategy within the sports institution. The researcher attributes this moderate level to numerous factors, encompassing the lack of qualified personnel within institutions, the absence of training programs for employees and administrators in this domain, and the failure of top leadership to recognize the significance of e-management or prioritize its implementation. A study by Laiadi (2021) similarly found that administrative requirements in sports institutions are moderately available, emphasizing the need to recruit specialized staff to guide these institutions toward adopting e-management and achieving their various prerequisites. Likewise, Raafat Radwan (2001) highlighted the importance of training human resources in information systems within institutions, considering it a top priority. Lout and Ben Mesbah (2019) highlighted the significance of fostering communication and technical skills among administrative practitioners in sports institutions by providing them with training programs in the field of information and communication technologies. Furthermore, Choayb and Omrane (2020) emphasized that having a well-trained and qualified administrative team, the backbone of administrative work, contributes to promoting the efficiency of sports institutions. Moreover, Ghrab and Ben Kennab (2018) underscored that investing in the qualification of specialized administrative staff across various fields of sports management enhances the overall efficiency of sports institutions.

The results presented in the table also support the hypothesis that administrative requirements contribute to the activation of e-management components in sports institutions. The researcher argues that these requirements form the foundation for creating a supportive administrative environment within the institution, playing a decisive role in the success or failure of any initiative. This involves offering highly efficient and skilled e-administrative leadership capable of effectively utilizing information and communication technologies. Such leadership contributes to strategic planning and lays the groundwork for the successful and effective implementation of e-management projects across departments, administrative units, human resources, and the institution's external environment. These findings are further supported by previous studies, including that of Rabie Shafiq (2017), who underscored that qualifying and providing well-

trained administrative staff is a fundamental requirement for e-management in institutions. Similarly, Laiadi (2021) confirmed the vital significance of administrative requirements in implementing e-management in sports institutions.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to identify the extent to which administrative requirements are available and their contribution to activating the components of e-management in sports institutions. Based on the results, we concluded the following:

- Administrative requirements are moderately available in sports institutions.
- The level of e-management implementation in sports institutions is moderate.
- Administrative requirements contribute to the activation of e-management components in sports institutions.

In light of these results, the following recommendations are suggested:

- Focusing on qualifying and training administrative staff in sports institutions, with specialization in information and communication technologies, to allow them to manage e-management systems efficiently.
- Providing training for human resources in sports institutions on the various components and elements of e-management.
- Establishing a dedicated body or department within sports institutions responsible for the planning, implementation, and monitoring of e-management strategies and projects.

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